

Work Life Balance Onwomen Police in Tiruchirappalli City

P.Shobana, M.B.A, M.C.S, M.Phil.,
Associate Professor & Research Scholar
Department of Business Administration
Shrimati Indira Gandhi College
Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Issue: 3

Month: January

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Received: 15.12.2018

Accepted: 19.12.2018

Published: 31.01.2019

Citation:

Shobana, P &
Na.Kanchana, P. "Work Life
Balance Onwomen Police in
Tiruchirappalli City." *Shanlax
International Journal of
Management*, vol. 6, no. 3,
2019, pp. 15–23.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2550059](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2550059)

P.Na.Kanchana

Professor, Christuraj Institute of Management
Christuraj College of Arts and Science
Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

The concept of women working in Indian heritage environment has always been challenging and much more of those women working in police force. A study of this research covered the challenges being faced by women police in Tiruchirappalli, South India. This research addressed the challenges on women police family bonding, women police stress, and health. A survey is conducted with 100 police personnel to perform quantitative analysis.

Keywords: Work Life Balance, Quality of Life, Stress, Health.

Introduction

P.Robbins (as cited in C.D. Balaji, 2016) Human resource management (HRM) refers to the management of people in organization. It is the systematic approach to achieve organizational objectives., through the optimal use of skilled employees. The objective is to ensure that the organization has the required human resources to achieve its goals. "HRM is concerned with the people dimension in management. It is a process consisting of four function acquisition, development, motivation, and maintenance of human resources. According to Gary Dessler(as cited in C.D. Balaji, 2016), "Human Resource management is the process of acquiring, training, appraising, and compensating employees and attending to their labour relations, health, safety and fairness concerns"

The Objective of HRM is to consider employee as human assets and human capital and not as costs, to enable the firm assess and obtain the right number and type of employees at the right time. The human element is the most vital, indispensable and inevitable aspect in every organization. Most importantly, the quality of human resource determines effective and efficient utilization of internally available and externally accessible resources.

In addition to the general challenges of employees in an organization, it should be recognized that female employees do have additional challenges in terms of various aspects. It should be also noted that the expectations towards working women have been tremendous without any compromise. Women in this century is also equally good and very competitive in both working and personal life.

Therefore, at times, work-life balance between the professional career and family/personal have become a greater concern, especially among the women employees since they do have additional responsibilities towards family management and development. Hence achieving work-life balance is an ultimate focal point of the women's life today.

Work Life Balance is a concept including proper prioritizing between work (career and ambition) and "Life Style" (health, pleasure, leisure, family, and spiritual development). This is related to the idea of lifestyle choice. Work life balance describes the relationship between your work and the commitments in the rest of your life, and how they impact on one another. Employers, employees and government want to maximize participation in the workforce. Work life Balance terms are used to describe the balance that an individual need between time allocated for work and others aspects of life. Areas of life other than work life can be, but not limited to personal interest, family and social, or leisure activities.

This paper is an initial attempt to explore the tough challenges faced by working women in maintaining a balance between their personal and professional life. Factors such as family and health/stress affecting the work-life balance of married working women have been examined in this paper.

Literature Review

There have been numerous definitions about Work Life Balance and following is a literature compilation of definitions from various authors.

Source	Definition
Clark (2001)	Satisfaction and good functioning at work and at home with a minimum of role conflict
Greenhauset al.(2003)	The extent to which an individual is equally in – and equally satisfied with – his or her work role and family role.
Frone (2003)	When there are low levels of inter-role conflict and high levels of inter-role facilitation.

Mark and MacDermid (1996)	The tendency to become fully engaged in the performance of every role in one's total system, to approach every typical role and role partner with an attitude of attentiveness and care.
Kirchmeyer (2000)	Achieving satisfying experiences in all life domains, and doing so requires personal resources such as energy, time and commitment to be well distributed across domains.
Hill et al. (2001)	The degree to which an individual is able to simultaneously balance the temporal, emotional, and behavior demands of both paid work and family responsibilities.
Grzywacz& Carlson (2007)	"...as accomplishment of role -related expectations that are negotiated and shared between an individual and his/her role partners in the work and family domains ." (p. 459)

McCarty and Atkinson (2012) stressed that balancing work-life is vital to achieve harmony in physical, emotional, and spiritual health. These indicators are vital to one's success. She also mentioned that psychological issues can be encountered, which is due to isolation from family friends.

Weerasinghe and Abeykoon (2017) concluded in his research that the personal factors are the significant association for job satisfaction and it was stressed that factors like flexible working arrangement and family friendly policies can be used to enhanced Work Life Balance.

PrashantLele (2018) revealed that police department provided Training Programmes on stress Management, communication skills, team building and attitudinal change, but inadequately. Therefore, this was resulted to problems such as alcoholic police constables, family problems, and psychological disorder. It should be noted that proper complete training programmes must be made available to personnel to eliminate the problems. Abendroth and Dulk(2011) proven that emotional family support has a positive impact on work life balance satisfaction. So it should be noted the family structure is one of the important factors towards a successful work life balance.

Lavanya and Thangavel (2014) proposed that flexi working hours should be made available to organization as compulsory policy, therefore it will help the women employees to be more responsible and to be productive at work.

Lunau T (2018) highlighted that there is an association between a poor work life balance and poor health across a variety of European countries. It should be noted that health can be certainly affected if work-life is not appropriately balanced. Hill et.al (2001) identified the main factors for work-life balance are stress influence, time management, work load, time pressure, overall feelings of job stress, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and labour turnover. The result of the study provided evidence of construct validity implication for theories of occupational stress as well as organizational practice.

The result of the Yildiz, S (2008) indicated that significant relationship between in addition to time balance, social relation work environment, are the other six factors also affected the well-being of the police. They are Rank, Department, optimism, isolation, income sufficiency and working days per week.

The study supported that work stress could lead to insomnia and partially disruption of work life balance. The strategies to prevent work demand from interfering with personal life such as clear work life boundary could probably decrease the risk of insomnia in employee who are under higher work stress.

Mehta and Kundnani (2018) also identified critical factors such as (i) the effects of organizational support, (ii) Work Family Conflict, (iii) Work place stress, and (iv) personality on work life equilibrium to reduce work-based stress.

Thevanes and Mangaleswaran (2018) has concluded in the research that Work Life Balance has a positive significant relationship between the job performance and quality of work life. The better work life balance in a given firm will always lead to improve the job performance of an employee. In addition, a good and healthy work life balance will be achieved.

Research Methodology

The study is a collection of both primary and secondary data. A structured questionnaire is designed to measure their work–life balance. This questionnaire was distributed to 100 women police in Tiruchirappalli police stations.

Data collection	Questionnaire
Type of Data	Primary data & Secondary data
Sample Size	100
Type of Questionnaire	Structured (59 Questions)
Research Instrument	Descriptive and correlation analysis
Sampling Technique	Simple Random Sampling

Research Objectives

1. To study the profile characteristics and the nature of women police in Tiruchirappalli.
2. To test the relationship between profile characteristics and work life balance and its factors.

Hypothesis Statements

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive association between age of the police women and work life balance and its factors.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant difference exist between work life balance and its factors across family type.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant difference exist between work life balance and its factors across academic qualification.

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant difference exist between work life balance and its factors across work experience.

Results and Discussion

Results and discussion are central steps in the research process. The aim of the analysis is to organize, classify and summarize the collected data so that they can be better comprehended and interpreted to give answers to the questions that triggered the research. Interpretation is the search for the broader meaning of findings. Analysis is not

fulfilled without interpretation; and interpretation cannot proceed without analysis; so, both are inter dependent.

A detailed analysis of the collected data has been attempted as per the objectives stated earlier. Hypotheses were also tested based on the findings

of the study, interpretations and conclusions were drawn. In this section, several statistical techniques for the analysis of data gathering such as descriptive analysis and inferential statistics, etc. are presented and discussed.

Table Distribution of Age of the Police Women in Tiruchirappalli City

		Age			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 - 30	52	52.0	52.0	52.0
	31 - 40	32	32.0	32.0	84.0
	41 - 50	16	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table shows that, 52% of the respondents are 20 and 16% of them are 41 to 50 age group. It is seen that to 30 years age group, 32% are 31 to 40 age group, majority of the respondents are 20 to 30 age group.

Table Distribution of Academic Qualification of the Police Women in Tiruchirappalli City

		Academic qualification			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative %
Valid	+2 and below	24	24.0	24.0	24.0
	Diploma	14	14.0	14.0	38.0
	UG Degree	50	50.0	50.0	88.0
	PG Degree	12	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table shows that, 24% of the respondents have qualification up to +2 standard, 14% of the respondents have qualification upto diploma, 50% of the respondents have qualification up to Under Graduate degree, and 12% of the respondent have qualification holding Post graduate degree. It is inferred that majority of police women have graduate level of education.

Table Distribution of marital status of the police women in Tiruchirappalli city

		Marital status			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative %
Valid	Single	32	32.0	32.0	32.0
	Married	62	62.0	62.0	94.0
	Divorcee	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table shows that, 32% of the police women are single, 62% police women are married and 6% of the respondents are divorce. It is inferred that majority 62% of the police women are married.

Table Distribution of Family Type of the Police Women in Tiruchirappalli City

Family type					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Joint	72	72.0	72.0	72.0
	Nuclear	28	28.0	28.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table shows that, 72% of the police women are with nuclear family. It is inferred that majority 72% joint family and 28% of the police women living of the police women are living with joint family.

Table Distribution of the Police Women Based on Their Working Experience in Tiruchirappalli City

Working experience					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative %
Valid	1 - 5	34	34.0	34.0	34.0
	6 - 10	20	20.0	20.0	54.0
	11 - 15	26	26.0	26.0	80.0
	16 - 20	12	12.0	12.0	92.0
	Above	8	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table reveals that, 34% of the police women have 20 years of experience and 8% of the police women one to five years of experience, 20% of the police women have above 20 years of experience. It is inferred that women have six to ten years of work experience, 26% majority of the police women have one to five years of experience, 12% of the police women have 16 to

Table Distribution of the Police Women Based on their Working Experience in Tiruchirappalli City

Designation					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Inspector	16	16.0	16.0	42.0
	Sub Inspector	35	35.0	35.0	51.0
	Constable	49	49.0	49.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table reveals that, 16% of the police women are constables. It is inferred that majority of the police women are constables. 35% of the police women are Sub-Inspector and 49% of the police women are

Table Distribution of the Police Women Based on their Time Spent on Domestic Activities in Tiruchirappalli City

Time spent on domestic activities					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid %	Cumulative %
Valid	Less than 2 hours	32	32.0	32.0	36.0
	2 - 4 Hours	28	28.0	28.0	60.0
	4 - 6 Hours	25	25.0	25.0	85.0
	More than 6 hours	15	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table shows the distribution of police women based on their time spent on domestic activities. 32% of the police women spent less than two hours on domestic activities, 28% of the police women spent two to four hours on domestic activities, 25% of the

police women spent four to six hours on domestic activities, 15% the police women spent more than 6 hours on domestic activities. It is inferred that majority of the police women spent less than two hours on domestic activities.

Table Distribution of the Police Women Based on Factors that Makes them to Go for Job

Factors that make to go for job					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative %
Valid	Personal Satisfaction	34	34.0	34.0	34.0
	Financial Independence	18	18.0	18.0	52.0
	Family Commitments	36	36.0	36.0	88.0
	Others	12	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table shows the distribution of police women responses based on the factors that makes them to go for the job. 34% of the police women go for the job because of their personal satisfaction, 18% of them are for financial independence, 36% of them are for family commitments and 12% of them are for other reasons. It is inferred that majority of the police women go for the job because of their family commitments.

Table Chi-square test between age group of the police women and factors of work life balance

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive association between age of the police women and quality of life and its factors

S.No.	Factors	Pearson Chi-square	p-value
1	Health & Quality of Life	9.265*	0.047
2	Work Efficiency	10.580*	0.032

(** p<0.01; * p<0.05.)

Table reveals the Chi-square test between age group of the respondents and factors of work life balance of police women opinion at three levels (low, moderate and high) among the variables health and quality of life, work efficiency, work life balance and age of the police women. As seen from the table 4.9, the p-value is less than 0.05, so the null hypothesis

is rejected at 5 percent level of significance. Hence it is concluded that there is an association between the age group of police women and health & quality of life ($\chi^2 = 9.265$, $p < 0.05$) and work efficiency ($\chi^2 = 10.580$, $p < 0.05$). Also from the table 4.9, the p-value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 percent level of significance.

Table Independent Sample T-Test Between Family Type of the Police Women and Factors of Work Life Balance

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant difference exist between work life balance and its factors across family type

Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
HQL	Equal variances assumed	6.360	.013	2.827	98	.006	2.80952	.99384
	Equal variances not assumed			2.356**	36.248	.004	2.80952	1.19271
WE	Equal variances assumed	.135	.715	-.534	98	.594	-.57540	1.07669
	Equal variances not assumed			-.525	47.471	.602	-.57540	1.09676

Table on t-test reveals that, the two tail significance for the family type indicates that $p < 0.05$ and, therefore, is significant. The two tail significance for the family type indicates that $p < 0.01$ and, therefore, is significant. It shows that there exists a significant mean difference among the police women on health

& quality of life ($t = 2.356, p < 0.01$). Also, the two tail significance for the family type indicates that $p > 0.05$ and, therefore, is not significant. It shows that there is no significant mean difference among the police women on work efficiency ($t = -0.534, p > 0.05$)

Table One-Way ANOVA Test Between Educational Qualification of the Police Women and Factors of Work Life Balance

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant difference exist between work life balance and its factors across educational qualification

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
HQL	Between Groups	237.483	3	79.161	4.057**	.009
	Within Groups	1873.077	96	19.511		
	Total	2110.560	99			
WE	Between Groups	228.906	3	76.302	3.542*	.017
	Within Groups	2068.094	96	21.543		
	Total	2297.000	99			

One – way ANOVA was applied to find the significant mean difference between educational status among police women and the result showed (Table 4.11) that there is a significant mean

difference in the educational status of the police women towards health & quality of life (F-value = 4.057, $p < 0.01$), work efficiency (F-value = 3.542, $p < 0.05$)

Table One-Way ANOVA Test Between Work Experience of the Police Women and Factors of Work Life Balance

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant difference exist between work life balance and its factors across work experience

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
HQL	Between Groups	116.509	4	29.127	1.388*	.024
	Within Groups	1994.051	95	20.990		
	Total	2110.560	99			
WE	Between Groups	141.101	4	35.275	1.554*	.019
	Within Groups	2155.899	95	22.694		
	Total	2297.000	99			

One – way ANOVA was applied to find the significant mean difference between work experience among police women and the result showed (Table 4.12) that there is a significant mean difference in the work experience of the police women towards health & quality of life (F-value = 1.388, $p < 0.05$), work efficiency (F-value = 1.554, $p < 0.05$),

Conclusion

Juggling between the obligations towards the families and expectation of the organization can have serious impact on personal life of an individual. Therefore, it is very important for women police personnel to maintain a healthy relation balance between professional and their private life. Women constitute a vital role in the workforce. Achieving a good work life balance between personal life and work life commitment is growing concern for every organization. Better work life balance leads to reduction of stress, thereby maintaining healthy environment leads to increase work efficiency.

This paper experienced an attempt to explore the tough challenges faced by working women police in maintaining and balancing between their personal and professional life. The various factors affecting the work life balance of women police have been examined in this study. Data were subjected to descriptive statistics and it was found that the problem faced by the women police is high. It hypothesizes that certain dimension of universe of the study encompasses women police, the work life balance affects their quality of life.

The epitome of successful women police

personnel lies in the implementation of work life balance policies that should be successfully streamlined and properly followed.

References

- Abendroth, AK., & Dulk, L, Den. ‘Support for the Work-Life Balance in Europe: The Impact of State, Workplace and Family Support on Work-Life Balance Satisfaction’, Work, Employment and Society, Doi: 10.1177/0950017011398892. vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 234-256, 2011.
- Balaji, CD. “Human Resource Management (Personnel Management)”, *Margham Publications*. 2016.
- Clark, AE. “What Really Matters in a Job? Hedonic Measurement Using Quit Data”. *Labour Economics*, vol. 8, pp. 223-242, 2001.
- Frone, Michael. “Work-Family Balance”. *Handbook of Occupational Health Psychology*. pp. 143-162.
- Greenhaus, JH., Collins, KM., & Shaw, JD. “The Relation Between Work-Family Balance and Quality of Life”, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*. DOI: 10.1016/S0001-8791(02)00042-8.
- Grzywacz, JG & Carlson, DS. “Conceptualizing Work-Family Balance: Implications for Practice and Research”, *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, DOI: 10.1177/1523422307305487 vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 455-471.
- Hill, (et.al). “Finding an Extra Day a Week: The Positive Influence of Perceived Job Flexibility

- on Work and Family Life Balance". *Family Relations*. DOI: 10.1111/j.1741-3729.2001.00049.x. vol. 50. pp. 49-58, 2001.
- Hill, Edward & Erickson, Jenet & Holmes, Erin & Ferris, Maria. "Workplace Flexibility, Work Hours, and Work-Life Conflict: Finding an Extra Day or Two. *Journal of Family Psychology*". JFP. *Journal of the Division of Family Psychology of the American Psychological Association (Division 43)*. DOI: 10.1037/a0019282. vol. 24. pp. 349-58., 2010
- Kirchmeyer, C 2000, "Work-Life Initiatives: Greed or Benevolence Regarding Workers' Work-life Initiatives: Greed or Benevolence Regarding Workers' Time?".
- Lavanya, L., & Thangavel, N., "Work-Life Balance Practices and Demographic Influence: An Empirical Approach". [online] *Iosrjournals.org*. Available at: <http://iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Vol16-issue1/Version-3/J01613104111.pdf> [Accessed 30 Oct. 2018]
- Lunau., TE. "A Balancing Act? Work-Life Balance, Health and Well-Being in European Welfare States. - PubMed - NCBI. [online] *Ncbi.nlm.nih.gov*". Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24567294> [Accessed 24 Oct. 2018].
- Marks, SR., & MacDermid, SM 1996, "Multiple Roles and the Self: A Theory of Role Balance. *J Marriage Fam*, vol. 58, pp. 417-432.
- Mehta, P., & Kundnani, N 2018, "Work-Life Balance at a Glance- a Synthetic Review". [online] *Borjournals.com*. Available at: <http://borjournals.com/a/index.php/jbmssr/article/viewFile/1930/1265> [Accessed 30 Oct. 2018].
- PrashantLele, D 2018, "Quality of Work Life of Police Constables with Special Reference to Wellness. [online] *Iosrjournals.org*. Available at: <http://iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Vol16-issue11/Version-4/G0161144651.pdf> [Accessed 30 Oct. 2018].
- Thevanes, N & Mangaleswaran, T "Relationship Between Work-Life Balance and Job Performance of Employees". [online] *Iosrjournals.org*. Available at: <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Vol20-issue5/Version-1/C2005011116.pdf> [Accessed 29 Oct. 2018].
- Weerasinghe, IMS & Abeykoon, ABMMM. "Impact of Work Life Balance on Job Satisfaction of Non-Gazette Officers in Sri Lanka Police 'With Special Reference to Badulla District' (February 26, 2017). *International Research Symposium, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka, IRSyRUSI 2015*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2924202>. 2018.
- Yildiz, Serdar, "Determinants of the Well-being of Police Officers in the Turkish National Police". *Electronic Theses and Dissertations*. 3784. <https://stars.library.ucf.edu/etd/3784>. 2008.